

Pentatomid bugs reduce rice grain quality in farmers' fields in Orissa

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We surveyed farmers' fields to study insects that reduce rice grain quality in Cuttack, Puri, and Balasore Districts, Orissa. In addition to rice stink bug *Leptocorisa acuta* (Thumb.), three new species of pentatomid bugs were found in both dry and wet seasons 1987-88. The bugs were identified as *Eusarcoris ventralis* Westw., *Mendia histrio* Fabr., and *Nezara viridula* Linn. (Pentatomidae : Heteroptera) at Zoological Survey of India, New Alipur, Calcutta.

Three villages were sampled per district. Bugs were collected from insecticide-free fields by net sweeping from five randomly selected 1-m² areas in each field. Five panicles also were collected randomly from each field; infested grains were counted to calculate grain damage (see table).

Insects were found during milky, soft dough, and hard dough stages in varieties Udaya, IR36, Ratna, MW10,

Grain damage in ricefields due to pentatomid bugs. Orissa, India, 1987-88.

Variety	Grain damage ^a (%)	
	1987 dry season	1988 dry season
Udaya	7.26 a	6.86 a
MW10	8.12 a	10.24 b
Ratna	13.23 b	14.75 c
	1987 wet season	1988 wet season
Savitri	3.97 a	2.89 a
Udaya	2.34 a	5.54 b
IR36	3.97 a	8.06 b

^aMean of 45 samples. Within columns and years, numbers followed by the same letter do not differ significantly.

and Savitri (CR1009). This was the first observation of *E. ventralis*, a stink bug, in India. Population densities in the dry season varied from 6.2 to 15.2 bugs (nymphs and adults)/m² in Udaya, MW10, and Ratna. In the wet season, populations varied from 1.73 to 8.54 bugs/m² in Udaya, IR36, and Savitri.

Green shield bug *N. viridula* also was found for the first time in India. Grains were infested during milky, soft dough, and hard dough stages. Population densities ranged from 5.5 to 9.6 bugs/m² during the dry season and 1.2 - 4.3 bugs/m² during the wet season. This bug was not found in Savitri.

M. histrio, a shield bug, was found for the first time in Orissa. It sucks the sap during the milky stage and reduces grain weight. Population densities ranged from 7.5 to 17.1/m² in the dry season and 4.9 to 14.0 bugs/m² in the wet season.

Insect populations were higher during the dry season. However, *M. histrio* predominated. Total grain damage ranged from 6.9 to 14.8% during the dry season and 2.3 to 8.1% during the wet season in different varieties. Grain damage differed significantly among varieties except in 1987 wet season. □

Weed management

Influence of herbicide carrier and application method on weed control

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We studied the influence of various carriers on the performance of the herbicide mixture anilofos + 2,4-D ethyl ester (EE) (0.30 + 0.51 kg/ha) in the 1988 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Applications were with a knapsack sprayer and 625 liters water/ha; sand-mix with 50 kg river-washed sand/ha; prilled urea (PU) at 25 kg urea/ha; sprinkler bottle with herbicide volume made up to 2 liters/ha; and hand weeding twice.

Herbicides were applied 6 d after transplanting (DT). Weed dry matter (DM) was measured 60 DT.

Weed flora included *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Cyperus iria*, *Marsilea quadrifolia*, *Ammannia baccifera*, and *Eclipta rostrata*.

Broadcast sand-mixed herbicide resulted in the least weed DM; PU as a herbicide carrier was equally effective (see table). (Using PU could reduce N

Effect of herbicide carrier on weed dry matter production and rice grain yield.^a Coimbatore, India.

Treatment ^b	Weed DM at 60 DT (g/m ²)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Knapsack sprayer (625 liters water/ha)	9.5 b	5.4 a
Sand mix (50 kg sand/ha)	6.5 a	5.4 a
Prilled urea (25 kg/ha)	7.8 ab	5.4 a
Sprinkler bottle	9.6 b	5.3 ab
Hand weeding twice (20 and 40 DT)	12.5 c	5.2 b

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level.

^bThe herbicide mixture consisted of anilofos at 0.30 kg/ha and 2,4-D EE at 0.51 kg/ha.

application, provided the herbicide and N application method do not cause excessive N losses.) Applying herbicide with the knapsack sprayer or sprinkler bottle resulted in higher weed DM, but significantly less than with hand weeding.

Grain yields were similar for all herbicide carrier treatments but were significantly lower with hand weeding. □

Effect of herbicide mixtures in transplanted rice

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We evaluated the efficiency of some new herbicide mixtures in transplanted rice